

INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY INTO ALMAJIRI EDUCATION PRACTICES: IMPLICATIONS ON THE PSYCHOSOCIAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN IN THE NORTHERN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study examines the integration of technology and its implications on the Almajiri education practices and child development in Northern Nigeria through a secondary data analysis within a system thinking framework. The Almajiri system, a traditional Qur'anic educational practice, involves the relocation of children from their families to study under Islamic teachers, often exposing them to socio-economic deprivation and limited parental care. While the system remains culturally and religiously significant, growing concerns exist regarding its impact on children's psychosocial well-being and developmental outcomes. Adopting a qualitative secondary research design, this study synthesizes existing literature, policy documents, reports, and empirical studies to explore the emotional, cognitive, and social consequences associated with the Almajiri system. A systematic review and thematic analysis approach were employed to identify recurring patterns, gaps, and contradictions in the literature. The study is guided by systems thinking to examine how interconnected factors such as poverty, family dynamics, cultural norms, and educational structures are collectively shape children's psychological experiences. The findings from this study revealed the complex patterns of psychosocial vulnerability, including emotional distress, social exclusion, and developmental challenges, alongside adaptive coping mechanisms exhibited by affected children. By integrating insights across multiple sources, the study contributes to a holistic understanding of the Almajiri phenomenon and provides evidence-based scenarios for policy reform and child-centered interventions that aimed at improving developmental outcomes in Northern Nigeria.

Keywords: Almajiri education, Child development, Psychosocial implications, Emotional well-being

Introduction

The Almajiri educational system has been in existence for over five hundred years. The system of education has played a significant role in the spread, development and acceptance of Islamic education in Nigeria especially, in the Northern Nigeria (Mohammed, 2015). Traditionally, the Alimanjiri practice of education requires the practice where young male children from predominantly rural communities are sent by their parents or guardians to distant locations purposely to acquire Qur'anic education. The nomenclature of the school system of education which was rooted in Arabic language has been

domesticated and popularly referred to as the "Tsangaya schools", "MakarantarAllo" respectively (Jamaluddin, 2017). For many families, this decision of sending the children out reflects deeply in the religious and cultural values of the northerners, as well as the economic realities of parents. In most cases, Northern parents often believe that enrolling their children in the Almajiri system of education will promotes the fulfillment of their moral and religious obligation to Islam and will enhance adherence to Islamic instruction, even when they lack the financial capacity to meet basic family needs (Njoku, 2020).

Estimates indicates that over ten (10) million poverty-stricken children live and beg on the streets of Northern Nigeria and this is as a result from the widespread practices of the Almanjiri education system in the area (Uwaezuoke-Onkonkwo, 2022). Considering other factors that surrounds the inefficiencies in the practice of this educational system, studies have indicated that due to inadequate funding, many founders of the school system as well as teachers within the system are unable to provide for the basic needs of the children under their care, including sufficient food, shelter, clothing, information communication mechanisms and health support (Gomment, 2020). Although every child has the right to health, basic education, and good nutrition, children that are enrolled in the Almanjiri system of education are often deprived of these fundamental rights where they are exposed to harsh means and coarse expectations to fend for themselves, this exposure and experiences of the children thereby force them to engaging in street begging and menial labour to supplement their daily upkeeps and for their survival. However, this level of their independency further forced and exposes them to physical hardship, vulnerable to exploitations, multiple forms of abuse, including psychosocial and sexual violence as well as unfavourable environmental conditions that undermine their overall well-being (Muhammad et al., 2023).

In recognition of the need to improve educational outcomes for all children and to align with global development goals, the Nigerian government has made efforts to mainstream and reform the Almanjiri education system. Specifically, the integration of Quranic/Tsangaya education into the Universal Basic Education (UBE) framework was adopted in several states, use of technological appliances especially by their malams for communication, displaying of alimajiri activities on screen, including

Kaduna State involvement, as part of broader efforts to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4), which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all (Muhammad, 2021). The establishment of formalized Almanjiri schools under the UBE system was intended to address the structural deficits of the traditional informal learning arrangements that previously characterized the education of Almanjiri pupils (Sarkingobir et al., 2019).

Despite these policy innovations, significant gaps remain in the implementation and effectiveness of educational reforms as well as integrating technological practices and use of gadgets or devices. Key challenges include inadequate funding, a shortage of skilled manpower, poor infrastructural facilities, poor initiatives in the use of technological devices and inconsistent school attendance among pupils (Muhammad et al., 2023). These constraints continue to undermine the potential gains of formalized Almanjiri education and have significant implications for the psychosocial development of children enrolled in the system. The persistence of psychosocial difficulties among Almanjiri children; even within reformed settings, suggests that structural integration alone cannot fully lessen the underlying developmental stressors associated with this educational pathway. Existing literature on the Almanjiri system has predominantly focused on its socio-economic dimensions, such as poverty, street begging, child rights concerns, and broader educational disparities. While these studies provide valuable insights into the material conditions of Almanjiri children, such as use of phones for social development and awareness, limited attention has been given to the psychosocial dimensions of child development within this context; particularly in terms of emotional, cognitive, and social functioning (Abubakar et al., 2014; Chukwu et al., 2016).

This gap in the research is problematic given the substantial evidence linking early environmental stressors with adverse developmental outcomes. The psychosocial consequences of prolonged separation from family with communication with the use of technology, limited care structures, and exposure to risk environments are profound and multidimensional, affecting not only individual children but also the communities and systems in which they live.

Moreover, there is a lack of comprehensive synthesis on the psychological impacts associated with the Almajiri system across different settings and interventions. By focusing on secondary data from studies conducted across Northern Nigeria, this research seeks to bridge this gap by providing an integrated understanding of how the technology in Almajiri educational system influences child development from a psychosocial perspective. This approach allows for a broader analysis of patterns, trends, and commonalities across existing research, facilitating a more systematic assessment of the developmental implications for children within the Almajiri system.

In adopting a system thinking framework, the study recognizes that psychosocial development is not shaped by isolated factors but emerges from the dynamic interplay of multiple systems, including family structures, cultural norms, educational practices, community environments, communication with modern technology and policy contexts (Krishnan, 2015). Systems thinking enables the analysis of feedback loops and interconnected influences that traditional linear models often overlook. For example, parental economic vulnerability influences decisions about child placement in Almajiri education, which in turn affects children's psychosocial well-being, ultimately influencing future educational and economic

opportunities thereby illustrating how individual, social media, economic, and policy systems interact to shape developmental outcomes. Understanding the psychosocial implications of the Almajiri system of education, is not only important for academic knowledge but also critical for informing policy and practice (Chowdhury et-al, 2017). Insights gained from this study are expected to contribute to evidence-based recommendations that can guide educational reform, child welfare strategies, and psychosocial support interventions aimed at improving developmental outcomes for Almajiri children. Such interventions are essential for advancing inclusive education and ensuring that all children, regardless of their educational setting, can achieve their full developmental potential.

This study aims to highlight the complex, interconnected influences on psychosocial outcomes, identify gaps in current understanding, and provide evidence that supports improved educational policy and child development practices. By synthesizing findings from multiple sources, this research contributes to a deeper, more holistic understanding of the developmental challenges faced by Almajiri children and underscores the importance of addressing psychological well-being as a central component of educational reform. However, the longstanding informal Almajiri system of education in Northern Nigeria has carelessly created a cycle of deprivation that negatively affects the social, economic, and psychological development of children enrolled in the system. The practice of sending young male children, often as early as four to twelve years of age, far from their homes to acquire Qur'anic education is widespread not only in Northern Nigeria but also in neighboring West African countries such as Ghana, Mali, Senegal, Chad, and Niger Republic (Odumusu et al., 2013). While intended to provide religious instruction and

moral guidance, this early separation from primary caregivers exposes children to numerous psychosocial stressors, including prolonged parental absence, social isolation, and inadequate supervision.

Concerns on the impact of technology in the Alimajiri system of education especially on the children has been raising issues which culminate to form questions that are very topical to research and are answer demanding. However, some of the questions could include the following: What are the Implications of technology in the Almajiri Education practices on the psychosocial development of Children in the Northern; What socio-economic and environmental factors contribute to the psychological and developmental challenges of Almajiri children; What are the social, emotional, and cognitive consequences of technology in the Almajiri education system on child development; How can the Almajiri education system be reformed to promote the psychological well-being and overall development of children through technology; What are the perceptions of Almajiri children, parents, teachers, and other stakeholders regarding the effectiveness of technology in the Almajiri education system respectively. (Hassana et-al, 2021).

It is on these pressing questions that have engulf the society and its educational system and as well seeking for answers from researchers on the ways forward in the sustainability of education of the young children that prompted the researchers to postulate the Research Objectives of examining the integration of technology into the Almajiri Education practices and its Implications of on the psychosocial development of Children in the Northern Nigeria which Specifically; identified the socio-economic and environmental factors that influence the psychosocial development of Almajiri children; assess the social, emotional,

and cognitive consequences of the technology in Almajiri education system on child development; proposed strategies for improving the Alimajiri education system to enhance children's psychosocial well-being and development as well as explored the views of Alimajiri children, parents, teachers, and stakeholders regarding technological practices in the Alimajiri education system and its impact on young children development.

Research Methodology

This study employs a literature review approach to examine the psychosocial predicaments and parental deprivation experienced by Almajiris children in Nigeria. The methodology involves a systematic and comprehensive review of existing academic literature, research reports, government policy documents, and relevant non-governmental organization (NGO) publications. The search strategy targeted three online databases: Google Scholar, Scopus, and EBSCO, to identify peer-reviewed journal articles, conference proceedings, and grey literature. The search was limited to publications in English from 2011 to 2025. Only Studies that were Nigerian focused issues that specifically addressed Alimajiri children and street children in Nigeria were all included in this study respectively.

The specific inclusion criteria for this study were: Studies focusing on the psychosocial conditions and parental care of Almajiris children in Nigeria, Articles written and published in English language within the last eleven to fourteen years, Studies that provide insights into the challenges, coping mechanisms, and societal implications of the Almajiris lifestyle and education pattern especially, in the Nigeria context, a two-stage screening process was used in which two independent reviewers evaluated the titles and abstracts of the selected publications. Disagreements were resolved through

discussions and consultations with a third reviewer. This procedure ensured over 90% inter-rater reliability. The methodological quality of the included studies was assessed using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP) checklist.

Pre-Colonial Almajiri Qur'anic School

The pre-colonial Almajiri education system in the Northern parts of Nigeria started operations as “the Tsangaya system of education”. The educational practice has been in existence since the early eleventh century and served as a foundation for moral and educational development of children and the socialization process of children (Muhammad, 2021). Prior to British colonization, northern Nigerian communities were largely literate, able to read and write the Qur'an, communicate in Arabic, and utilize their local vernaculars. During this period, Islamic faith played a central role in political and collective life, and Qur'anic literacy was highly valued (Muhammad, 2023 and Odumusu, 2013;). According to Maigari (2017), the British colonizers encountered a well-structured educational system in the Tsangaya institutions that spanned from basic introductory lessons to advanced Qur'anic studies comparable to university-level scholarship. At the beginning of colonial rule, the system required minimal support to adapt to modern educational standards.

Trends in the histories describe that the Qur'anic teaching system uses an individualized approach in instruction, allowing pupils to learn at their own pace. Students begin by rehearsing verses written on wooden slates until mastery is achieved. Teachers then incrementally introduce new verses. Once students complete the recitation stage, they proceed to memorization, selecting chapters of the Qur'an that align with their cognitive abilities. Recitations are corrected for pronunciation and orthography, enabling pupils to progress systematically (Maigari,

2017). At this early state of operation, aspects of traditional technology manifested in the operation of the educational system in such areas as preparing slates, writing materials as well as the ink. All these in their crude form made the system working then and thus, pave way for the introduction of the modern technology especially the communication and information technology into the system.

Post-Colonial Almajiri Qur'anic School

Sarkingobir et al., (2019) asserts that the exclusion of Qur'anic pupils from the formal school system marginalized Almajiri children, leaving them disconnected from governmental engagement and employability due to a lack of literacy and numeracy skills. Almajiri schools primarily focus on Qur'anic recitation, often neglecting broader educational competencies. Jamaluddin (2017) noted that traditional governance and leadership experienced a significant decline with British colonial rule, resulting in the systematic marginalization of Qur'anic education. Tsangaya institutions lost official support and their graduates became economically and socially disadvantaged. As formal education gained momentum to modern technological practices, Arabic and Qur'anic literacy lost official status, and Roman numerals were introduced as a replacement (Kabir, 2012). However, studies emphasized that colonial policies undermined Tsangaya schools, prompting parents to continue sending their children to Qur'anic schools despite the shift toward secular education.

Muhammad (2013) explains that Tsangaya teachers bear full responsibility for the schools, including feeding, clothing, and sheltering the pupils. Consequently, the schools fail to meet educational and material objectives, and pupils often grow into uneducated and impoverished adults. The traditional Qur'anic learning system collapsed, largely due to the lack of state support, and has not fully recovered. Laws governing education were made without

consideration for Tsangaya schools, leaving them to survive solely through community efforts. The historical neglect of these schools by colonial authorities mirrors the contemporary indifference of some elites, who often blame Almajiri children for social vices among northern Nigerian youth (Maigari, 2017).

The present-day Almajiri System of Education

In 2010, the Nigerian Federal Ministry of Education estimated approximately 9.5 million Almajiris in northern Nigeria, while Odumusu et al. (2013) estimated nearly fifteen million across the nineteen northern states, with sixty-five percent from the northwestern region. Around ninety percent do not attend formal

The peak of Qur'anic literacy in northern Nigeria and regions of West Africa coincided with this period, with inspection systems established to monitor learning outcomes (Gomment, 2020).

Modern integration of Almajiri schools aims to combine traditional Tsangaya institutions with formal curricula, incorporating subjects such as English, mathematics, integrated science and technology, social studies, and vocational skills, alongside Qur'anic studies including memorization, Tajweed, Arabic, Islamic studies, Tauhid, Hadith, Fiqh, and Sira (Isiaka, 2015; Yusha'u, Tsafe, Babangida, & Lawal, 2013). The federal government, through agencies such as Universal Basic Education and Tertiary Education Trust Fund, developed models for incorporating Almajiri schools, including community-based day schools, boarding schools, and integration into existing Islamiyyah and Ma'ahad schools (Media Trust, 2013; Isiaka, 2015).

Despite these interventions, Almajiri children often face severe deprivations of their basic child rights. Boarding school students

public schools. Kano city alone had 1,560,000 Almajiris in 2008, and in 2009, 1.6 million Almajiris were enrolled in the 26,000 Tsangaya institutions across Kano State. Historically, the Tsangaya schools provided ethical and educational instruction to Nigerian Muslim communities. Before British colonization in 1824, children attended local Qur'anic schools, commonly referred to as Makarantar Allo or "school of the slate," living at home while receiving instruction and guidance (Kabir, 2012). Jungudo and Ani (2014); Hoechner (2013) report that the system originated in the eleventh century under the Borno Islamic kingdom, later expanded by Usman Danfodio, who formalized Qur'anic education and Islamic law across northern Nigeria.

frequently rely on community contributions for food and lodging, while day students from distant areas endure long commutes without adequate provisions (Hoechner, 2013 and Odumusu et al., 2013). Historically, funding and patronage came from Zakat, community support, and parental contributions, with children engaging in labor to reciprocate. Today, however, the majority survive through begging and casual labor, exposing them to hunger, poor shelter, health risks, abuse, and psychological distress

The initial objective of the Almajiri system was to instill elementary spiritual, ethical, and social values while providing Qur'anic instruction. Islam entered northern Nigeria in the eleventh century, spreading through trade networks and Arab scholars, bringing Islamic jurisprudence, theology, and Arabic literacy (Kabir, 2012). The current predicament of Almajiri children began with British colonial invasion, which undermined the authority of traditional rulers, removed financial support for Tsangaya schools, and introduced formal education, forcing children into streets for

survival. Consequently, Almajiris now occupy a vulnerable underclass in northern Nigerian cities, lacking skills, education, techniques and basic needs, which has profound implications for their psychosocial development and well-being (Hansen, 2016; Tufeiru, 2016; Kabir, 2012; Hoechner, 2013; Odumusu et al., 2013).

Psychosocial Difficulties among the children of Almajiri schooling system

The challenges associated with the Almajiri system are complex and intersect across social, educational, economic, and health domains. These include poorly structured learning environments with substandard infrastructure for both educational engagement and daily living, a lack of adequate adult supervision and parental care, persistent loneliness and social isolation, poor nutrition, heightened insecurity, exploitation, and societal negligence (Abubakar et al., 2014; Chukwu, Haruna and Fiase, 2016). Including poor skills in the use of technology especially for social interaction.

The absence of an organized curriculum, coupled with the system's exclusion from formal education frameworks and modern technology, further disadvantages these children and limits opportunities for holistic development. Consequently, morbidity and mortality rates among Almajiri children remain high, with long-term negative effects that often extend into adolescence and adulthood (Abdullahi, 2020). Exposure to chronic stressors at childhood, such as prolonged separation from family, economic hardship, social exclusion, and survival demands in informal environments, has been linked with increased susceptibility to mental health problems in later life. The psychosocial consequences include emotional instability, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, substance abuse, and other psychological maladjustments (Bogart et al., 2014; Hager & Leadbeater, 2016). If these issues are not

addressed early, they tend to persist and deepen, ultimately emerging as entrenched societal problems that challenge families, communities, and national development agendas.

The underprivileged way of life of the Almajiri children positions them as one of the most downgraded groups of children in the society. The Almajiri children are exposed to numerous vices and experience some constant distress as they observe other children enjoying parental care and attention, parental loves and affections, as well as creating strong bonding with their parents and caregivers. They often receive leftover food from children younger than themselves and are expected to acknowledge it by saying "Allah yasaka" (may God acknowledge your gesture). Odumusu et al. (2013) and Hoechner (2013) note that Almajiris are particularly distressed when they realize the comforts that they are deprived of parental protection, adequate food, safe accommodation, and love. Over time, they develop a perception of society, including their parents, as cruel and selfish.

The absence of parental love and societal sympathy leads some Almajiris to engage in hard drugs, while others become thugs, errand boys, or laborers. Vojdani and Shaibani (2016) argued that; children of the street are socially and psychologically disadvantaged due to the persistent failure to meet their immediate needs, requiring more attention and supervision than their parented peers. They observed further that such children often display lower internal coherence compared to children raised within families. Unlike street children in other countries who may escape due to family crises or abuses, it is however ascertained that the Nigerian Almajiris are deliberately sent out by their parents.

Another aspect of difficulties that need to be examined is the Low Self-Esteem. By

definition, Self-esteem implies the ability of the children or an individual child's perception about their worth or personality. Abubakar et al. (2014) describes self-esteem as a subjective evaluation of one's emotional value. Self-esteem can be shaped by the life experiences and the messages these experiences convey about personal worth. For Almajiris, repeated exposure to neglect and deprivation reinforces a sense of insignificance; they consume discarded food, wear second-hand clothing, and sleep on the streets while parented children enjoy comfort and security. Krishnan (2015) emphasizes that early childhood experiences significantly influence self-perception. The Almajiri children that are sent away from home at a young age, face hardship, destitution, and rejection, leading them to adopt a worldview dominated by survival and injustice. Hewitt identifies early experiences that foster negative self-beliefs of which are common among all the categories of the Almajiri children.

They however include: Regular punishment, neglect, or maltreatment, Poor parental standards, Inability to meet peer-group expectations, Exposure to others' stress or distress, Membership in stigmatized families or groups, Absence of praise, encouragement, warmth, or affection as well as Being treated as different at home or school. Negative self-perceptions can also emerge later in life through bullying, abuse, persistent stress, or traumatic events (Obimakinde and Shabir, 2023). For Nigerian Almajiris, the combination of early deprivation, lack of parental care, harsh discipline, lack of exposure to the use of basic technological equipment and absence of future prospects contributes to enduring low self-esteem.

Many Almajiri children experience extreme deprivation including chronic hunger, malnutrition, and insufficient shelter. Their survival largely depends on street begging, small-scale menial labor, or reliance on

community charity, often resulting in irregular meals and diets dominated by carbohydrates (Jungudo and Ani, 2014; Odumusu et al., 2013). The lack of stable sources of nutrition and income, poor access to information and communication technology, combined with unsafe living conditions and exposure to exploitation, violence, and societal neglect, places these children at heightened risk for psychological distress and developmental challenges. Despite its cultural and religious significance, the Almajiri system neglects fundamental child development needs including emotional support, safety, and social inclusion. Children in this system are vulnerable to emotional instability, low self-esteem, social maladjustment, anxiety, and other forms of psychological dysfunction. These challenges threaten their ability to attain optimal cognitive, social, and emotional development and, if unaddressed, may persist into adolescence and adulthood, perpetuating cycles of poverty and social marginalization.

In another perception, Deprivation of Parental Care is one major aspect of the series of difficulty that children of the Tsangaya education system have been experiencing. Parental care is a multi-faceted concept that varies across cultures, classes, and locations (Lynn, 2013). For this study, parental care encompasses moral guidance, education, financial support, and preparation of a child for societal norms. Child deprivation occurs when responsible adults fail to meet physical, emotional, educational, or medical needs, deny basic resources, or fail to provide love, attention, and respect (Kassie, 2016). Scholars further argued that sending Almajiris to boarding schools without frequent parental visits or communicating through social media or phone call, may be intended to allow focus on studies. However, scholars such as Jungudo and Ani (2014) contend that many Almajiris are effectively abandoned on the streets under the guise of Qur'anic education, left to

navigate life independently. Lynn (2013) emphasized that children require guidance to develop decision-making skills, competence, and personality. Without clear boundaries, regulation, and supervision, children face insecurity and developmental risks. Almajiris, left to determine their own lives, lack these essential structures. Neglect in their upbringing fosters delinquency and exposure to negative behaviors. The absence of parental authority leaves Almajiris reliant on instinct, leading to hardship, anger, and psychological distress (Odumusu, 2013).

Overview of Policies and practices in the Almajiri system of education in Nigerian

Government have put in place Several policies that are designed to influence the lives of street children, this is either directly or indirectly as the case may be. Some initiatives such as the Child Rights Act, Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), the Salamanca document for the special need and vulnerable children, the Education for All (EFA), Universal Basic Education (UBE) and the African Charter on the Rights and Welfare of the Child aim to protect and improve the welfare of young people. In conjunction with Article 31 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC). Vojdani and Shaibani (2016) emphasize a child's rights to leisure, play, and participation in cultural and creative activities. These policies are intended to address the holistic development of children, including Almajiris, whose lives are often affected by neglect, deprivation, and lack of access to information and communication technology as well as quality education.

Specifically, the Nigerian Universal Basic Education programme is one major landmark in the policies provisions and laws of the education of the Nigerian child. The Universal Basic Education Scheme was introduced in 1999 as part of the Federal Government's efforts to restructure basic education in

Nigeria. This initiative is embedded in the Constitution of Nigeria Section 18 (1) and (3) of the 1999 Constitution), which mandates that the government shall ensures equal and adequate educational opportunities across the nation. According to the Universal Basic Education Law of 2004, Part 1 Section 2 (1), "Every Government in Nigeria that is; the states and area councils/local governments; shall provide compulsory, free and universal basic education for all children of primary and junior secondary school age. Section 2 (2) stipulates that every parent or guardian must ensure that their child or ward attends and completes primary and junior secondary education. Section 2 (4) outlines penalties for non-compliance, including reprimand for a first offense, and a fine of N2,000 or one-month imprisonment, or both, for subsequent violations (Odumusu et al., 2013).

It becomes pertinent to reiterate here that the Universal Basic Education (UBE) represents both international collaboration and domestic policy priorities. Global frameworks such as the 1961 Addis Ababa Seminar, the 1990 Jomtien Declaration, and the Education for All Action Plan highlighted the importance of basic education for skill acquisition and national development. Section 15 of the Act defines Universal Basic Education to include nine years of formal education, non-formal education, adult literacy programs, skills acquisition programs, and the education of special groups such as migrant children, nomads, girl-children, widows, women, Almajiri pupils, and persons with disabilities. The Act recognizes Almajiri children as part of its mandate to provide basic education. Estimates from the Ministerial Committee on Almajiris Education place the number of Almajiris in Nigeria at approximately ten million, while other studies suggest up to sixteen million children roam the streets (UNICEF, 2014). Neglecting these children not only violates their fundamental rights but

also threatens the country's prospects for home-based technology development and socioeconomic transformation (Odumusu et al., 2013).

The Child Rights Act serves as another policy aspect of the Alimajiri children and schooling practices. The approval of the Child Rights Act (CRA) in 2003 by the Nigerian National Assembly generated hope for improving the welfare of Almajiri children. The Senate proposed the formation of the National Commission for the Eradication of Child Destitution, known as the "Almajiris Bill," sponsored by Umaru Argungu and thirty-one other senators. This bill aimed to penalize any unregistered Almajiri school or Tsangaya operator with a two-year jail term (Odumusu, 2013).

The federal government also sought to integrate formal education with Qur'anic education to transform Almajiri pupils into productive members of the society. Some of the key provisions of the Child Rights Act include:

Part 1, Section 1: states that; Every action concerning a child, whether by an individual, institution, service, administrative, judicial, or legislative authority, must prioritize the best interest of the child. The Article II, under Section a: states that; Children are entitled to dignity and respect and shall not be subjected to torture, mental, physical, or emotional injury, neglect, abuse, or maltreatment. Furthermore, in Article 12, Section 1; it is stated that Every child has the right to leisure, rest, and participation in sports and games appropriate for their age. Article 13 on its part states that: Every child is entitled to health services, including the provision of adequate nutritious food, potable water, a hygienic environment, and safety measures to prevent disease.

The Article 14 of the Child Right Act, in section 2 indicates that, every child has the

right to parental care, maintenance, and protection according to the parent's or guardian's means, with legal enforcement where necessary. Accordingly, Article 15 thus indicates Children have the right to free and compulsory universal basic primary education, which the Nigerian government at all levels is indebted to provide for all children irrespective of gender, tribe, religion, culture, location status, etc. By implications, these policies and legislative frameworks are directly relevant to the protection, development, and psychological well-being of the Almajiri children, whose lives have historically been shaped by deprivation, marginalization, and inadequate access to quality formal education and backwardness in the technological awareness and development.

Recommendation

1. There is need for the concerned governmental agencies and policy makers to strategized effective implementation of reforms that will integrate technological practices and use of gadgets or devices in alimajiri system of education for improvement and standard
2. There is need for the government of the day to enforce policy agencies on funding mechanism for the alimajiri system of education to grow, develop and contribute meaningfully to the national sustainability goals.
3. There also need for the boards, ministries of educational, concerned sectors as well as teacher training institutions to come on board for ensuring proper implementation of curriculum design for these categories of children by educating the teachers of alimajiri, the proprietors of the school system and promoting efficiency in skilled manpower, adequate infrastructural facilities, positive initiatives in the use of technological

devices and consistent school attendance in the system

4. There is need for proper and adequate orientation and enlightenment programmes for parents about their unavoidable responsibilities on their offspring. There is need for school feeding practices in this system as well as proper record keeping as this will help keep track of parents visits to their children and will reduce the psychosocial distress of child development within this context; particularly in terms of emotional, cognitive, and social functioning

Summary and conclusion

In summary, this study investigates the integration of technology into the Almajiri education system and its implications on the psychosocial development of children in Northern Nigeria by analyzing existing secondary data within a systems' thinking framework. The study provided detailed accounts of Almajiris children's experiences, parental neglect, and psychological challenges were judged to be of moderate level to high quality education technological advancement of the Alimajiri system of schooling. Key themes and findings were extracted accordingly, synthesized sequentially and presented narratively. The findings from this study thus, revealed the complex patterns of technology deficient, psychosocial vulnerability, including emotional distress, social exclusion, and developmental challenges, alongside adaptive coping mechanisms exhibited by affected children. The review also examined the roles of stakeholders, including governmental agencies, religious institutions and the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), in addressing the welfare and education of the Almajiris children. By integrating insights across multiple sources as examined above, the study contributes to a holistic understanding of

the Almajiri phenomenon and provides evidence-based scenarios for policy reform and child-centered interventions that aimed at improving developmental outcomes in Northern Nigeria.

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